

Development of Digital Learning Platform for Aeronautics and Space Technology

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Abstract

In the advanced era the development and usage of interdisciplinary applications is very much helpful to understand the basics of each and every phenomenon of technology, engineering, mathematics and science. This article is focused on the development of digital learning platform for better understanding of science behind the aeronautics and space. The developed digital platform is name as T.E.M.S academy to make users to learn and get certified for the lectures or courses organized by International institutions and organizations. The article will show the step by step development of the digital platform from domain setup to how it helps the users. Here our users are mostly the students and faculty with the background of aerospace science.

Keywords : T.E.M.S academy, Digital learning, Aerospace Engineering, Sensei LMS

1. INTRODUCTION

The modern internet era have given many solutions to the problems of communication and transmission of datas from one sector to another sector. The modern technology like smartphones have also made the usage of internet not only for communication, securing the datas, to understand artificial intelligence and machine learning, virtual learning have also developed in the educational sector and industrial sector. The historical change in educational sector, the internet plays a major role in it. Development of millions of websites in various platforms with different applications also helped the consumers to use for entertainment, employee management system, project management system, social media, news channel, online store platforms also have been made in the last three decades in large numbers. Figure 1. shows some of the web pages that are widely used current world by consumers.

Figure 1. Top websites based on the number of time visited in a month

There are some educational platform which is already existing for various field of study. Figure 2 shows the top educational platforms which are currently available for the students to engage and upgrade their knowledge.

Figure 2. Number of learners in millions in top learning platforms.

2. DOMAIN AND HOSTING

A domain name is an identity string which precises an area of admin, control or power within the Internet. A service of web hosting is one of Internet hosting work type which gives singles and administrations to develop a website reachable through the World Wide Web [www]. The development of T.E.M.S academy has to starts with new domain and hosting. But in support with WINGS OF AERO [WOA] which have already have a separate .in domain and windows shared hosting, T.E.M.S academy is developed with subdomain under WOA with a url of academy.wingsofaero.in. Figure 3 represents the WOA domain registration with single domain windows hosting [USA – TX] which is run with plesk hosting platform. The platform used for content management is WordPress [WP] which is an open source content management developed using php.

Figure 3. shows the WOA domain and hosting.

Plesk hosting platform will show the administration control of WOA domain, to create a new subdomain, to install different content management systems which application prefers as shown in figure 4. There are three different content management systems available under plesk namely, WP, Joomla, Drupal as indicated in figure 5. For the easy access and security purposes the development of T.E.M.S academy is done with WP platform by considering its advantage over other two platforms. Once the content management system WP installed, the WP files will be available under academy.wingsofaero.in directory. Modifying the files will effect in the website also. Figure 6 indicates the location of WP files. Now the domain, hosting and content management system is ready for our digital learning platform.

Figure 4. shows the subdomain of T.E.M.S academy in Plesk – web host edition

Figure 5. represents three featured applications available under plesk web hosting

Figure 6. shows the WP files in file manager after installation of WP application

3. DIGITAL LEARNING PLATFORM

After successful installation of WP, login to the admin panel by using following url academy.wingsofaero.in/wp-admin, the login credentials have to be obtained in the plesk panel itself. Once the login is successful, the dashboard panel will be available as shown in figure 7.

Figure 7. shows the T.E.M.S academy admin dashboard

As this article focus on digital learning platform development, the plugin menu will be focused a lot and not discussing about other columns or menus like posts, media, pages and appearance sections. Figure 7 showing the developed dashboard after the installation of various plugins for the website. The posts section will help to create a new post and control the old posts which you have created. The media section will help to add new media file like image, video, documents or to delete the one. Comments section shows all the comments or replies given by your visitors about any posts or media files. The tools and settings will allow one to change the general available options. By clicking at the top right corner of the window where it is mentioned “Howdy – Pon Maa Kishan A”, one can get edit profile option to change password and other personal details not only for the admin also for the users.

4. LMS PLUGINS

In website or any software the word “plugin” represents the additional software components depending upon the required application. Even though WP is a content management system, it requires a plugin to develop a digital learning platform. There are different learning platform plugins are available in WP.

Table 1. shows the course management plugins and its parameter details

Sl. No	Plugin Name	Number of User
1	Learn Press	80,000
2	Tutor LMS	9,000
3	Lifter LMS	10,000
4	MasterStudy LMS	10,000
5	Sensei LMS	6,000

Figure 8. shows the plugins available for Learning Management System [LMS]

From Table 1 and Figure 8, shows the plugins available for developing a digital learning platform with number of installation. For T.E.M.S academy, the Sensei LMS developed by Automatic is selected. This LMS is simple and easily accessible for the person who is not that much familiar with coding and other factors. In figure 8 also represents the Sensei LMS is already installed and activated in this subdomain.

5. SENSEI – LMS

After successful installation and activation of Sensei LMS setup will be loading making to set the basic and necessary details of LMS. The advantage of Sensei LMS is the availability of various options. The analysis tab shows the performance of the learners along with their details, courses and lesson through figure 9. The grading tab gives the option to understand whether the learners have graded successfully or not. Also the grading tab will allow you an option to grade course-wise as shown in figure 10.

Figure 9. shows the analysis tab of Sensei LMS

Figure 10. shows the grading tab of Sensei LMS

The message tab helps the admin to read the messages send by the learners from their respective courses or lectures as shows in figure 11. The admin or instructor can reply directly through the message tab to their learners. The data updates, settings and extensions will allow the admin to enhance the plugin as per their requirement as shown in figure 12.

Figure 11. shows the message tab of Sensei LMS

Figure 12. shows the data updates tab of Sensei LMS

Courses tab under sensei LMS will help to add new course or edit previous courses, delete courses, etc., Also the courses can be categorized under this section as shown in figure 13.

Figure 13. shows the course tab of Sensei LMS

Lecture tab under sensei LMS will allows to create new lectures and to link the lectures to the new or old courses. The Prerequisite to the lecture can also be added under this tab as shown in figure 14.

Figure 14. shows the lecture tab of Sensei LMS

The certificate tab under sensei LMS will helps to verify the certificates generated through LMS and also helps to create new certificates and certificate templates as shown in figure 15.

Figure 15. shows the certificate tab of Sensei LMS

The question tab under sensei LMS will help to create questions and allows to edit already generated questions through LMS, the questions can be linked to any lesson through this link as shown in figure 16.

Figure 16. shows the question tab of Sensei LMS

By using the above tabs and options, the next step is to add new aerospace courses with thumbnails, tags, keywords, lessons, corresponding quiz questions, etc.,

The other plugins added in the domain are SEO tools, classic editor and elementor to enhance performance of the platform.

6. TEST RUN AND RESULT

The front or first page of T.E.M.S academy platform is displayed as shown in the figure 17. with web-page menus like courses, my profile, my courses, messages, login/logout button.

Figure 17. shows the front page of T.E.M.S digital learning platform

As an initiative two courses titled “Introduction to Space Tourism” and “Introduction to Space Materials” have been added in the digital platform for the students to learn and get certified. The

students and enthusiastic people of Aerospace Engineering have enrolled into the platform and started to learn the course. Figure 18. shows the result of number of people enrolled for the test run courses through T.E.M.S academy.

Figure 18. shows the number learners enrolled in their respective lectures/courses.

Once the participant or learner who have started to learn the course will get digital certificate after successfully answering the quiz questions and completing all the lectures of the course. A sample of certificate is shown in the Figure 19.

Figure 19. shows the sample certificate generated after completing the course/lecture.

From figure 9 and figure 10, we can understand the analysis and grading of any particular course.

7. CONCLUSION

As mentioned earlier even-though there are many learning platforms available for digital learning platform. The developed digital learning platform T.E.M.S academy will focus on the aeronautics and space science. From the analysis of two test courses, a lot of improvement is needed to be done in the platform to make user friendly. The future work is to develop a progressive web application [PWA] for T.E.M.S academy so that the learners can easily access to the course from the app itself. Also a special focus on marketing will be also made to enhance the features of the T.E.M.S academy and make it available for free to all the aerospace enthusiastic people.

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